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Biodiversity Research for Sustainable Development

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Abstract

This paper deals with Biodiversity research for sustainable development is interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary which is relatively new to the India. The argument for it and characterization of what it should be is thus derived partly from the failure of the traditional research approach, sometimes called “lessons learned”, to effectively provide relevant knowledge support to biodiversity conservation. On the other hand, biodiversity research for sustainable development has recently been initiated in the country from which empirical data can be gathered on the character and process of such a research approach, and which ones work. This paper deals with concern about biodiversity research, biodiversity research in sustainable livelihood frame work and major objectives of biodiversity research programme. It outlines the need for collaborative biodiversity research and its implications and issues in biodiversity research. This paper concludes with some policy measures towards biodiversity conservation. Biodiversity, ecosystems and the essential services that they deliver are Central pillars for all life on the planet, including human life. They are sources of food and essential nutrients, medicines and medicinal compounds, fuel, energy, livelihoods and cultural and spiritual enrichment. Deforestation should be strictly prohibited. Environmental laws should be followed strictly. The useful and endangered species of plants and animals should be conserved in their nature as well as artificial habitats. Public awareness should be created regarding biodiversity conservation and its importance

Keywords: Biodiversity, sustainable development, climate change. Environmental sustainable

Introduction

Biodiversity is an element of the natural resource base, which is a component of the ecosystem and landscape. As part and attribute of the ecosystem, biodiversity, particularly that of plants, serves as the primary producer that provides the energy that is used and channelled to different components of the ecosystem, interacts with other components of the ecosystem, and becomes a major determinant of the ecosystem's structure and its functions. These interactions determine the productivity, stability, and sustainability of ecosystems including functions such as reproduction and regeneration, nutrient and water cycling, biotic stability, and others.

It could be noted that biodiversity is a key feature or element of the natural resource base, which when it interacts with the technology and socio-economic dimensions, determines the pathway of development. If the existing technological, socio-economic and institutional processes erode biodiversity and its functional elements as a component of the natural resource base, the resulting development process will not be sustainable in the long run. However, if biodiversity is well managed in that its structure and functional relations are kept intact, then a more sustainable pathway for economic development could likely be attained.

The Concern about Biodiversity Research

Many researchers in the field of biodiversity have pointed out that “we know very little of what we pretend to preserve”. This theme, however, until the recent past has referred to biological knowledge such as the lack of a complete inventory of flora and fauna, and, at a higher level, the lack of a good understanding of their ecological relationships.

Biodiversity research, therefore, has so far been mostly on the biological side, resulting in conservation policy that protects species, with the more enlightened ones directed at protecting ecosystems. Recently, however, there has been a realization that this “knowing very little” refers not just to the biology of it but more importantly to the lack of a good understanding of the socio-cultural, economic, and political dynamics that cause loss of biodiversity on one hand, and its effective conservation on the other.

In the recently held World Summit for Sustainable Development (WSSD), this “poverty and environment nexus” has been questioned. As the WSSD was actually a long drawn out debate between South and North perspectives on sustainable development, the agreed text that eventually came out in a way reflects an alternative perspective worth looking into. The agreed text points at the “possible nexus between poverty and environment.” This WSSD consensus recognizes that there is a nexus between poverty and environment but that there may also be other more important causes of environmental degradation outside of poverty.

Sustainable livelihood framework

Biodiversity in the ground or in the water or in a landscape is primarily determined by those who manage and use them - fisher folks for fisheries, farmers for farms and so on. If we use the sustainable livelihood framework, this will help us analyze and comprehend why and how people do what they do with the natural resource base. This is because user groups will primarily have the objective of engaging in activities, including conservation and use of genetic resources, to obtain outputs for sustainable livelihood - whether it is for income; for food security; and for cultural, aesthetic, and environmental values. The sustainable livelihood framework is based on the premise that user groups and their households have five capital assets, which they can use for various livelihood outcomes. These are human, financial, physical, social and natural assets. Human capital refers to the skills, knowledge and information, ability to work, health, and others. Natural capital consists of land, water, livestock, wildlife, biodiversity, environment, air, and others. Physical capital may consist of transport, shelter, energy, communication, and other infrastructures and technology. Financial capital consists of savings, credit, remittances, and pension, among others. Social capital consists of social networks, groups, trust, access to wider institutions, ability to demand, and others.

Biodiversity research programme

The Biodiversity research program has three main objectives are to: develop a society-driven approach in the conservation, management,

and sustainable use of biological resources; Build and strengthen national capacity for biodiversity research; and Promote research cooperation on equal footing among North and South researchers. The Biodiversity research programs’ objectives, in turn, have four guiding concepts for biodiversity research: Location-derived and development-oriented; Promotes multi-stakeholder participation; Systems-oriented and promotes interdisciplinary interaction; and Integrated ecosystems or landscape approach.

Knowledge and Research

There is a need to conduct research to lessen the dependency of the communities on forest biodiversity resources through intensification of research in forest areas. Research to design and establish ecological networks and networking within the biosphere reserve areas in India; Further develop the knowledge base for monitoring, conservation, and livelihood development, and; Continue the scientific network collaboration of the researchers and research institutions including international networking.

Practice and Implementation

Efforts could be made to recognize and support the sustainability of the socio-cultural heritage of the indigenous people in tribal areas; continue and intensify the stakeholders' awareness on the values of and participation in planning and decision-making regarding biodiversity conservation in forest areas improve access to financial assistance and further development of infrastructural services; and identify the comparative advantages.

Collaborative Biodiversity Research

Research and sustainable development work should be mutually reinforcing. Research that is work-driven by societal needs should produce essential, accurate, and verifiable information on which future decisions and actions for development are to be based. Sustainable development work, on the other hand, engages civil society and governments in a process that uses knowledge from relevant research for effective development action. As conceived, Biodiversity research programme should be a collaborative research programme for development founded on three important principles.

Society-driven approach for biodiversity research

“The biodiversity research programme should contribute to the conservation, management, and sustainable use of biological and genetic resources.” In this context, setting the research agenda should involve relevant stakeholders in research, government, and society, who are likewise potential beneficiaries of the research results: policymakers, non-government offices

(NGOs), private sector groups, and local communities.

Developing a comprehensive approach that aims to integrate support for collaborative research and for building and strengthening national capacity for biodiversity research as a central concern of the Programme, strengthening national capacity will encompass thorough human resource capacity building, particularly for scientific research that is relevant for development. Training of people, institutional strengthening, and creation of mechanisms for continuing capacity development in the country where the research is being undertaken are key strategies in this comprehensive approach.

Research cooperation on equal footing

“Southern and Northern researchers participate as equal partners... and must have an equal say in policymaking and decision-making processes... Such equality is essential for sustainability of partnerships over the long run.” These principles have been reiterated in the various stages and levels of formulating and developing the biodiversity research programme. In general, biodiversity research programme should be Location-derived and development oriented. In this context, the research agenda, priorities, and methods should be based on the needs of the people and biodiversity in the area. Research questions should be derived from the people’s identification of problems and potential solutions, which are meaningful for their own development. In this way, the relevance and fullness of research will be established from the beginning.

Promoting multi-stakeholder participation

This involves not only the scientific research community but most importantly, local communities and stakeholders, including local governments and NGOs. There should be constant interaction with and feedback from stakeholders to make the research responsive to local development needs. Their participation will enhance the mechanisms for research to be translated into policies, programmes, and day-to-day practices that will conserve biodiversity and resources.

Systems-oriented and interdisciplinary

The conceptual framework of the research should be holistic, i.e. it should examine and aim to understand the interaction of different elements of the system. To do this, research must bring together the natural and socio-economic and cultural components and their interactions, which affect biodiversity. Researchers of various disciplines in the natural and social sciences and those honed in crosscutting or multiand interdisciplinary studies should come together in this approach.

Integrated ecosystems and landscape approach.

Interactions of elements within an ecosystem are fundamental to studying biodiversity. The interactions among the elements of contiguous ecosystems, however, are equally important to provide a holistic and integrated analysis. Materials, energy, and people flow through adjoining ecosystems with positive or negative effect on these. A landscape approach can use methods of analysis associated with the watershed or catchment area that spans the uplands, lowlands, and coastal and marine ecosystems. Political-administrative units cover landscapes, so that they, in particular, will benefit from this broader and integrated analytical approach for making better decisions.

Biodiversity research methods

It includes the participatory approach and interdisciplinary methodologies for assessment, benchmarking, locating and characterizing biodiversity valuation of biodiversity, enhancing its values, and others. Further, there is a need of institutional analysis and capacity building, policy analysis and formulation. It is essential to have community empowerment for biodiversity management and identification of appropriate interventions for enhancing values of biodiversity for improving livelihoods is need of the hour Efforts could be made to promote appropriate policies in international property rights to balance the promotion of a proper balance between exclusive private rights and 'common rights' to obtain the greatest and equitable benefits from biodiversity and its elements

Regional Research Framework

A possible regional program should support the national biodiversity plan or program of each Southeast Asian country including the management of protected areas and be aligned with the Millenniums development goals. It should highlight common research areas that these countries can work on or how these countries can help meet each others' objectives in biodiversity conservation and research. A regional program will clearly delineate priorities as well as complementarities in research, establish collaboration with more impact and support including that of funding, and gain that value-added of working together.

National Biodiversity Research Programmes

The national biodiversity programmes could be made on the basis of institutional arrangements; policy; conduct of research for development; most effective collaboration mechanisms and approaches between North and South scientific communities; most effective unit for managing biodiversity; effective interdisciplinary methodologies; most useful participatory methods; and community

empowerment. These approaches can be scaled-up in the region by comparative analysis of methodologies, participatory approaches, and intervention strategies. However, upscaling would need guidelines to implement research for development, institutional arrangement, and the transformation of results or lessons learned into policy levels at all levels.

Common areas of concern

The biodiversity conservation should focus on strategy – development research and management of biodiversity in and around protected areas especially terrestrial and coastal or the two ends of the landscape, core map – with emphasis on coastal and marine areas related to population distribution Benchmarking of basic studies or information on biodiversity for development and sustainability. There is a need of data management for biodiversity research in terms of establishment of databases, inventory, taxonomy and data management of these information on various species, focus on key taxa and species. In this context, monitoring and evaluation of biodiversity research for sustainable development could be made in terms of capacity building needed for a landscape approach – standardized methods of monitoring; participatory methodologies; inventory, taxonomy of key species etc. In biodiversity research for sustainable development, the first issue is difference in technical capacities. The unequal level of research capacities and skills between North and South partner researchers and institutions caused delays in the implementation of projects. To effect the envisaged collaboration, capacities have to be brought to similar if not complementary levels. In biodiversity research for sustainable development, the second issue is difference in research interests and agenda. Despite efforts to orient North and South researchers to a common research framework and agenda, there are natural personal and institutional biases towards favourite or historical topics.

Priority Researchable Areas

In order to promote biodiversity research for sustainable development, the following prior research areas should be considered. Formulation of a strategy on nature and Indian biodiversity protection. Revision of the laws on nature conservation for elaboration and approval of the National Assembly. Issuance of a decision on an institutional framework for protected area management between relevant ministries, agencies, and local authorities. Development of investment mechanisms and policies for the protected area system from central to local level. Issuance of guidelines or rules to formulate investment projects for the protected area system. Issuance of regulations for scientific study on biodiversity, ecology, and management of the protected area

system. Issuance of a regulation for international cooperation on conservation and protection of natural resources and their sustainable use. Development of a policy for the involvement of local people and communities in conservation activities in and around the protected areas..

Conclusion

It could be seen clearly from the above discussion that in recognizing the scientific, economic, and cultural importance of its biodiversity, India has already taken a number of steps to preserve its resources over the past decade. It has developed several strategic planning documents from 1980 such as the National Conservation Strategy, The National Plan for Environment and Sustainable Development, the Tropical Forestry Action Plan, and the Biodiversity Action Plan. Biodiversity conservation is clearly one of India's greatest challenges. The protection of the natural ecosystems of India and the species, which depend on them, is vital not only for India but for the world. Therefore, in the future, India needs to strengthen institutional arrangement and international collaboration for conservation management, laws and regulations governing biodiversity conservation, policies concerning property rights, and protected areas and species by developing some high priority projects or programmes for biodiversity conservation with support from the government and international organizations.

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Conflicts of interest

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